

THE EFFECT OF SEA WATER ABSORPTION IN
PULTRUDED COMPOSITE RODS

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ABSTRACT

Five different composite systems, AS4/vinyl ester (VE), IM7/VE, AS4/PPS, Kevlar 49/VE, and Kevlar 149/VE, were studied for the effect of sea water absorption. Specifically, rod specimens were immersed in synthetic sea water over a period ranging from 8 to 14 months until they reached saturation. Transverse tensile strengths were measured in a diametral compression test while longitudinal compressive strengths were measured using an end-loading fixture. Sea water immersion has degraded the transverse tensile strength of all pultruded rods by at least 20%, except for Kevlar 49/VE and IM7/VE rods which showed only a 9.6% and a 9.3% decrease, respectively. The longitudinal compressive strength degraded the least in Kevlar 149/VE and the most in AS4/PPS, a decrease of 2.4% and 28.8% respectively. Since these strength properties are sensitive to the matrix and interfacial strengths, it is concluded that the absorbed water sufficiently degrades the matrix and the interface. The degradation of the fiber/matrix bonding resulting from water absorption has been verified on photomicrographs also.

KEYWORDS: Pultrusion; Absorption; Damage; Strength; Testing/Evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION

Pultruded composite rods are being considered for application in tethers for tension leg platforms [1-3]. Compared with steel tethers, composite tethers can provide higher specific stiffness and strength while being highly corrosion resistant. The composite tether is constructed of a set of small diameter composite rod elements assembled with an outer protective layer to form a rope. While pultrusion is a cost-effective process ideally suited for

the fabrication of long unidirectional rods, pultruded composites still do not enjoy the same degree of quality as autoclave molded composites because of the difficulty with applying enough compaction pressure. Therefore, the former may be more susceptible to salt water absorption and subsequent degradation.

The effect of moisture content on the mechanical behavior of continuous fiber reinforced composites has been shown [4-6] to adversely affect composite properties which are matrix- and interface-dominated. The maximum moisture content of a composite is dependent on the constituent materials, interface, and void content, as well as on environmental conditions such as the presence of pressure and/or high temperature. Because of their geometric limitations, pultruded rods can not be tested using the usual test procedures for flat panels. Two of the easiest test methods to characterize the matrix/interface-controlled strength of pultruded composite rods are the diametral compression test and the longitudinal compression test. The diametral compression test has been used in the past to determine the splitting tensile strength of intact rock core specimens for drilling purposes [7] and on bituminous concrete disc specimens to evaluate the elastic modulus or creep compliance [8]. Most recently, the diametral compression test has been used as a quality control test for pultruded composite rods [9]. Specimen failure in this test is initiated at the center where a transverse tension-compression biaxial stress state is present. The effect of this biaxial stress state on the specimen failure and the measured strength of the rods was discussed in [9,10]. It was estimated that the apparent strength measured by the diametral compression test could vary between $0.72Y$ to $1.24Y$, where Y is the transverse tensile strength from uniaxial tension test. Despite this variation, diametral compression is a valuable test to characterize the effect of different environmental conditions on the matrix/interface-controlled properties of pultruded composite rods.

Piggott and Harris [11] studied the longitudinal compressive behavior of several pultruded composite rods using an end-loading fixture. Their results indicate that for rods with low v_f , the compressive strength was proportional to the matrix yield stress, σ_{my} , and the compressive modulus was an inverse exponential function of σ_{my} . Piggott later [12] concluded that stiff straight fibers, strong interface, and a high matrix yield stress are necessary to improve the compressive strength of a composite. Hahn and Williams [13] have also shown that stiffer resin improves the compressive strength of a composite by forcing a kinking mode of failure. Additionally, Parry and Wronski [14] have shown that the superposition of hydrostatic pressure enhances the compressive behavior of polymeric composites by increasing matrix yield stress and forcing a kinking mode of failure.

The present paper investigates the effect of sea water absorption in pultruded composite rods by determining the extent of degradation in the diametral compressive and longitudinal compressive strengths. Three Gr/Ep and two Kevlar/Ep composites are studied to provide a better understanding of the sea water effect on pultruded rods. Further, salt water degradation of the fiber/matrix interface is examined on photomicrographs of the rod specimens.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials: Materials used in this study include two Kevlar®/epoxy systems: Kevlar-49/vinyl ester (VE) and Kevlar-149/VE, and three graphite/epoxy systems: AS4/VE, AS4/PPS, and IM7/VE. Several long pultruded rods of each material were received from two different manufacturers. Some rods were kept in synthetic sea water at room temperature and monitored periodically until near saturation, while others were kept at room conditions and tested as-received. The conditions of the pultruded rods are described in Table 1.

2.2 Salt Water Absorption: Three rods of each composite were cut with length to diameter ratio approximately equal to 50 to ensure that diffusion and salt water pickup occurred primarily in the radial direction. The specimens were then weighed and subsequently dried in a vacuum oven for approximately one month at 50°C until a stable plateau equilibrium weight was achieved. This desorption process ensured that there was no initial trapped moisture in the rods. Therefore, moisture content measured during immersion in the salt water was the total moisture content. Once dried, rods were immersed in a storage vessel containing ASTM D1141-52 sea salt water at room temperature. The weight gain of each composite rod was monitored periodically by weighing the wet rod, and the moisture content was calculated using

$$M = \frac{w - w_d}{w_d} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where w is the measured weight of the specimen and w_d is its dry weight. The maximum attained moisture content of each rod material [15] is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Conditions of pultruded composite rods prior to testing

Rod Material	Diameter (mm)	V_f	<u>As-received</u> Moisture Content (%)	Immersion Time (Months)	<u>Saturated</u> Moisture Content (%)
AS-4/VE	6.35	0.67	0.23	13	0.50
AS-4/PPS	6.35	0.48	0.02	14	1.50
IM7/VE	5.08	0.68	0.12	8	0.40
Kevlar-149/VE	6.35	0.65	0.94	13	1.50
Kevlar-49/VE	5.08	0.67	1.40	12	4.10

2.3 Diametral Compression Specimens: The as-received and saturated specimens, 28mm-long, were cut from pultruded rods. Each specimen was then loaded perpendicular to its longitudinal axis to failure in a displacement controlled test machine. The failure of the specimen was accompanied by a reduction in load. The apparent transverse tensile strength corresponding to the load P at failure was calculated by the following expression [16],

$$\sigma_x = \frac{P}{\pi R L} \quad (2)$$

where R and L are rod radius and length, respectively. Following testing, some of the rods were separated along the fracture plane and examined on a scanning electron microscope.

2.4 Longitudinal Compression Specimens: Dry and saturated specimens 30mm-long were cut from pultruded rods. Specimen ends were carefully leveled to form a 90° angle with the loading direction. The specimen was then placed in a fixture similar to that suggested by Piggott [1] leaving a gage length of 16 mm, and the assembly was centered in an IITRI compression jig. Compressive load was applied to the specimen moving the cross head at a rate of 0.635 mm/min. Five dry specimens and five saturated specimens were prepared for each composite except for IM7/VE, for which saturated specimens were not available.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Test results are summarized in Table 2, and the wet-to-dry strength ratios of mean strength in transverse tension and longitudinal compression are shown in Figure 1. It is apparent from the results that salt water has a deleterious effect on both transverse tensile and longitudinal compressive strengths of the pultruded composite rods, as expected from previous studies [4,17-19]. The saturated rods for all composite systems studied show a decrease in transverse tensile strength of at least 20%, except for Kevlar 49/VE and IM7/VE rods which show only a 9.6% and 9.3% decrease, respectively. On the other hand, longitudinal compressive strength degraded the least in Kevlar 149/VE and the most in AS4/PPS, a decrease of 2.4% and 28.8% respectively. It is interesting to note that the rods which show the most decrease in transverse tensile strength are not the same rods which show the most decrease in longitudinal compressive strength. This is because longitudinal compressive strength is not only dependent on the properties of the matrix and the interface but also on the fiber.

3.1 Longitudinal Compressive Strength: Results shown in Table 2 indicate that for all composites the coefficients of variation are within 8%, thus reflecting consistency of the strength data. In addition, Figure 1 indicates that Kevlar 149/VE and AS4/PPS rods are, respectively, the least and most degraded by salt water immersion. Unfortunately, the saturated IM7/VE rods were not available.

Salt water immersion has resulted in a significant degradation of the compressive strengths of the pultruded rods, except for the Kevlar 149/VE material. As Table 2 shows the strength values of Kevlar 149/VE are very consistent, and the reduction in strength due to salt water immersion is only 2.4%, very low compared with other pultruded rods. Moreover, Kevlar 149/VE compression specimens, as-received and saturated, failed in a shear mode along a plane at 45° to the axis of the specimen, Figure 2. However, Kevlar 49/VE showed a totally different behavior in compression; wet specimens showed a 24% decrease in strength, and specimens failed in crushing mode on a plane perpendicular the specimen axis, Figure 2. Graphite/epoxy rods show significant strength degradation as a result of salt water immersion. The AS4/VE rods, which register the highest compressive strength (1010 MPa) among the

Table 2. Results of the diametral compression and longitudinal compression tests

Rod Material	Diametral Compression				Longitudinal Compression			
	As-Received		Saturated		As-Received		Saturated	
	No. Tested	Mean Strength* (MPa)	No. Tested	Mean Strength* (MPa)	No. Tested	Mean Strength* (MPa)	No. Tested	Mean Strength* (MPa)
AS-4/VE	8	28.2±6%	6	18.3±10%	5	1010±5%	5	794±1.8%
AS-4/PPS	8	6.8±16%	6	4.6±9%	5	507±7.4%	5	361±3.3%
IM7/VE†	5	20.4±6%	6	18.5±13%	5	816±7.5%	---	---
Kevlar-149/VE	5	9.5±14%	6	7.1±24%	5	247±0.1%	5	241±1.0%
Kevlar-49/VE	10	5.2±2%	6	4.7±8%	5	208±7.3%	5	157±7.8%

*Mean strength ±Coefficient of Variation% (COV), where $COV = (\text{standard deviation} / \text{mean strength}) \times 100\%$

† Saturated IM7/VE rods were not available for longitudinal compression testing

tested rods, show a 21.4% strength reduction when saturated. Similarly, the saturated AS4/PPS show a 28.8% strength reduction as compared with the as-received rods. The AS4/PPS rods have failed in a longitudinal splitting (or transverse tensile failure) mode as shown in Figure 2, where a longitudinal crack can be seen in the AS4/PPS specimen. This is an indication of a poor interfacial bond in AS4/PPS rods. All AS4/VE and IM7/VE specimens failed abruptly along a plane perpendicular to the specimen axis in a crushing failure mode. It should be pointed out that there was no discernable difference between the as-received and wet specimens with regard to their failure mode in longitudinal compression.

3.2 Transverse Tensile Strength: It is surprising that the saturated AS4/VE rods, with only 0.5% moisture content, show the greatest decrease in strength (a drop of 35%), while the Kevlar 49/VE rods, with the highest moisture content of 4.1%, show a much smaller decrease (a 9.6% decrease). Even with the sharp decrease in transverse tensile strength, the AS4/VE rods still show one of the highest average strengths (18.3 MPa) among the tested materials. The AS4/PPS rods, like the AS4/VE rods, show a sharp decrease in strength of 32%. The Kevlar-149/VE rods also show a large reduction, i. e. 25%. The IM7/VE rods show only a 9.3% decrease in strength, which is most likely due to the presence of a strong interfacial bond as will be discussed later. Wet-to-dry strength ratios shown in Figure 1 demonstrate that wet Kevlar 49/VE and IM7/VE retained most of their strengths ($\approx 91\%$), whereas wet AS4/VE and AS4/PPS rods preserved only 65% of their dry strengths.

3.3 Microscopic Examination of Failed Specimens: Rod failure in diametral compression occurs as a result of the transverse tensile stress reaching a threshold value at the center of the rod cross section, therefore initiating a crack which under increasing load propagates along the loading plane, Figure 3. Photomicrographs of representative failure surfaces for the material systems saturated in salt water and tested using diametral compression are presented in Figures 4-6. The photomicrographs show the failure surface exposed when the salt water saturated

specimen was separated after testing into two half cylinders. The differences in fiber/resin distribution and the quality of the interface are observed in these representative specimens. It should be pointed out that the fracture surfaces of the as-received rods tested in diametral compression were previously examined [9].

Areas of fiber pullout and poor bonding were characteristic of the fracture surface of the Kevlar 149/VE rods, shown in Figure 4a, where saturated rods showed a decrease in strength of 25%. Similarly, the fracture surface of the Kevlar 49/VE rods shown in Figure 4b is characterized by regions of bare and clean fibers and areas of fiber pullout. This indicated poor bonding and/or the degradation of the interfacial bond due to immersion in salt water.

The fracture surfaces of the AS4/VE specimen shown in Figure 5a reveals areas of good bonding intermixed with areas of fiber pullout and regions where the interface had been degraded. The messy fracture surface indicates that bonding was strong, thereby explaining the relatively high transverse tensile strength. Also, there are areas on the fracture surface where the failure surface appeared ductile. It is believed that the absorbed salt water acted as a plasticizing agent and caused the ductile fracture behavior. The fracture surface of the AS4/PPS rod is characterized by a very poor interfacial bond demonstrated by the areas of fiber pullout and "clean fibers" as shown in Figure 5b. In addition, there was evidence of matrix stretching, likely caused by the absorbed salt water acting as a plasticizing agent in the thermoplastic matrix. Also shown in Figure 5b are regions where the interface degraded in a sort of "pitting" that occurred as a result of salt water immersion. It should be pointed out that the as-received rods that were tested and examined previously [9,15] showed no signs of this type of interface degradation. Interfacial pitting most likely occurred because the interface acts as a pathway for the transport of solutions. Examination of the fracture surface for the IM7/VE rods, shown in Figure 6, revealed the presence of very few regions of bare fibers intermixed with regions of good interfacial bonding throughout most of the rod. The regions with the good interfacial bonding were characterized by a rough fracture surface, indicating that the rod resisted fracture, thus yielding the highest transverse tensile strength of all saturated rods.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The degree of strength degradation caused by salt water immersion depends not only on the amount of moisture absorbed, but also the type of pultruded composite system and the quality of interfacial bonding within the rod. Sea water immersion has degraded the transverse tensile strength of all pultruded rods by at least 20%, except for Kevlar 49/VE and IM7/VE rods which showed only a 9.6% and a 9.3% decrease, respectively. The longitudinal compressive strength, however, degraded the least in Kevlar 149/VE and the most in AS4/PPS, a decrease of 2.4% and 28.8% respectively. Thus, rods which showed the most decrease in transverse tensile strength are not the same rods which showed the most decrease in longitudinal compressive strength. Photomicrographs of failed saturated specimen revealed variable interfacial bond degradations resulting from sea water absorption.

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Figure 1. Wet -to-dry strength ratio in transverse tension and longitudinal compression

Figure 2. Longitudinal compression specimens after failure showing rods failure modes

Figure 3. Typical tensile failure of a rod specimen tested in diametral compression

Figure 4. Photomicrograph of the fracture surface of (a) a Kevlar 49/vinyl ester rod (600X), and (b) a Kevlar 149/vinyl ester rod (600X) tested in diametral compression

Figure 5. Photomicrograph of the fracture surface of (a) an AS4/vinyl ester rod (600X), and (b) an AS4/PPS rod (2000X) tested in diametral compression

Figure 6. Photomicrograph of the fracture surface of an IM7/vinyl ester rod (800X)